

ABSTRACT BOOK

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INDIVIDUAL CHOICES IN THE LIGHT OF SDGS AND GLOBAL CHALLENGES

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The global challenges of the present are so numerous, large and complex that an individual often feels helpless, unsafe and endangered. Seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) represent a universal call to contribute comprehensively to solving global challenges, in order to eradicate poverty, ensure peace and prosperity for all, and also protect the environment. They include climate changes, economic inequalities, as well as innovation, sustainable consumption, peace and justice. The interconnection of SDGs is reflected in the fact that the key to the success of one goal is often to solve the challenges that are part of another goal. Partnership and pragmatism are an imperative within the activities of achieving goals and making appropriate choices for a sustainable improvement in the lives of future generations.

Bearing in mind the interweaving of SDGs, it is necessary that health professionals act much wider and

more comprehensively, and not only to target at goal 3 (health and well-being).

The goals should also be achieved through behavior, not exclusively through knowledge and counseling. In line with this, the role of hygiene as a basic preventive and public health branch of medicine may need to be reassessed, but to remain recognized, present both within our own space and wider.

It is necessary to insist on the individual responsibility of health professionals, ie on individual contribution through healthy lifestyles and individual choices that are presented by personal example and way of life in accordance with SDGs.

KEYWORDS: sustainable development goals, poverty, climate, health professionals, responsibility